

МОДЕЛЮВАННЯ ЗАДАЧ ТРАНСПОРТУ ТА ЕКОНОМІКИ

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IDENTIFYING THREATS IN COMPUTER NETWORK BASED ON MULTILAYER NEURAL NETWORK

Purpose. Currently, there appear more often the reports of penetration into computer networks and attacks on the Web-server. Attacks are divided into the following categories: DoS, U2R, R2L, Probe. The purpose of the article is to identify threats in a computer network based on network traffic parameters using neural network technology, which will protect the server. **Methodology.** The detection of such threats as Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune in the computer network is implemented on the basis of analysis and processing of data on the parameters of network connections that use the TCP/IP protocol stack using the 19-1-25-5 neural network configuration in the Fann Explorer program. When simulating the operation of the neural network, a training (430 examples), a testing (200 examples) and a control sample (25 examples) were used, based on an open KDDCUP-99 database of 500000 connection records. **Findings.** The neural network created on the control sample determined an error of 0.322. It is determined that the configuration network 19-1-25-5 copes well with such attacks as Back, Buffer_overflow and Ipsweep. To detect the attacks of Quess_password and Neptune, the task of 19 network traffic parameters is not enough. **Originality.** We obtained dependencies of the neural network training time (number of epochs) on the number of neurons in the hidden layer (from 10 to 55) and the number of hidden layers (from 1 to 4). When the number of neurons in the hidden layer increases, the neural network by Batch algorithm is trained almost three times faster than the neural network by Resilient algorithm. When the number of hidden layers increases, the neural network by Resilient algorithm is trained almost twice as fast as that by Incremental algorithm. **Practical value.** Based on the network traffic parameters, the use of 19-1-25-5 configuration neural network will allow to detect in real time the computer network threats Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune and to perform appropriate monitoring.

Keywords: network traffic; threat; neural network; sampling; hidden layer; hidden neurons; training algorithm; number of epoch; error

Introduction

There have recently been increasingly frequent computer penetration reports and attacks on Web-server. Very often, intruders bypass established protective devices. Attacks are carried out in a very short time and the variety of threats is constantly increasing, which prevents from detecting and preventing them with standard protective

equipment [2–3]. Existing approaches are characterized by a number of features that hinder their use: low speed of work; poor accuracy [1, 13, 15]. To eliminate these shortcomings, a neural network technology is proposed [1–4, 6–12]: multilayer perceptron; Kohonen network; neuronetty network (hybrid system).

Attacks are divided into the following categories [2, 14–15]: DoS (Back, Land, Neptune, Pod,

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Smurf, Teardrop), U2R (Buffer_overflow, Loadmodule, Perl, Rootkit), R2L (Ftp_write, Quess_passwd, Imap, Multihop, Phf, Spy, Warez-client, Warezmaster), Probe (Ipsweep, Hmap, Portsweep, Satan). DoS attack is characterized by the generation of a large amount of traffic, which leads to overload and lockup of the server; U2R attack (User to Root) involves receiving by a registered user of administrator's privileges; R2L attacks (Remote to Local) are characterized by access of an unregistered user to a computer from a remote machine; Probe attacks include scanning of ports in order to obtain confidential information.

At the present stage, various solutions are offered for the modernization of existing computer networks, in particular, in the information and telecommunication system of the Prydniprovskya railway [5, 16].

Purpose

To develop a method for detecting threats in a computer network based on network traffic parameters using a multi-layer neural network in the Fann Explorer program.

Methodology

To detect threats we used 19 network traffic parameters (x_i) [14]: package type (TCP, UDP, ICMP and others); service type (http, telnet, ftp_data, eco_i, private); flag; number of bytes from source to recipient; number of bytes from recipient to source; number of hot indicators; successful entrance; number of compromised conditions; number of connections to the host for 2 s; number of connections to one service for 2 s; percentage of connections to the service for 2 s; percentage of connection to different hosts; number of connections to the local host installed by the remote side for 2 s; number of connections to the local host installed by the remote side, uses 1 service; percentage of connections to this service; percentage of connections to other services; percentage of connections to the host with the port number of the source; percentage of connections with a rej-type error for the recipient host; percentage of connections with a rej-type error for the service. On the basis of the values of the set of the

attack features, it is necessary to carry out the classification conclusion (y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5) of the following threats: Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune. Detection of threats in a computer network is based on the analysis and processing of data on the parameters of network connections using the TCP/IP protocol stack. As initial data we used KDDCUP-99 database of 5,000,000 connection records (the sequence of TCP packets for the final period, the start and end points of which are clearly defined, during which the data is transmitted from the sender's IP address to the recipient's IP address using the defined protocol). As a mathematical tool of problem solution we took the neural network (NN) of the configuration 19-1-25-5, where 19 is the number of neurons in the input layer, 1 is the number of hidden layers, 25 is the number of neurons in the hidden layer, and 5 is the number of neurons in the resulting layer.

Findings

Purpose and features of the Fann Explorer program. Fann Explorer is portable graphical environment for developing, training and testing neural networks that supports animation training, creation, provides an easy to use browser-based interface for fast artificial neural network (Fann library). FannKernel provides a neural network with the kernel, which is a multi-threaded kernel, so several neural networks can be studied and explored at the same time. This program has a fairly wide-ranging functionality for training and researching neural networks. The View menu allows you to open three main windows: Controller (main panel, which defines all the parameters for teaching the neural network), Error plot (dependence graph of the mean square error on the number of passed training epochs), Weight Graph. On the Topology tab, you can get acquainted with the main characteristics of the topology (Fig. 1).

The Testing menu allows you to check how well the neural network is being trained and the ability to edit incoming data. The test results are presented as a comparison graph of the mean square error with the reference value shown in Fig. 2.

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algorithm, some tasks will achieve more effective solutions with this algorithm.

Error Function: Linear is a linear error function that calculates it as the difference between the actual result given by the neural network and the expected value that the operator has set; Tangential (Tanh) is a function of error, which makes a large deviation during training. The idea of the function is that it is better if 10 neurons have an error of 10% at the output, than one of them will have an error of 100%. This function is the default error, but it can lead to poor training outcomes if you set the Training rate too high.

The functions of Hidden layer activation and Output layer activation are as follows: Symmetric, Asymmetric-Linear, Sigmoid, Stepwise, Threshold.

The Training menu manages the training process of NN, sets the adaptation parameters of the NN link weight factors such as: the number of training periods, the value of the mean square error, the initial values of the NN link weight factors using the Initialize button.

Testing of neural network. Figure 5 shows a graph of NN testing of 19-1-25-5 configuration after training and testing on the appropriate samples. The bright line on the graph shows the expected response, while the darker one is the actual response. The test error is 0.05868; the lines almost coincide, so NN is well suited to the task.

Fig. 5. NN testing schedule

Analysis of the results. The NN of 19-1-25-5 configuration was trained according to the standard algorithm for error propagation and the training

speed of 0.699. Activation function is sigmoid (symmetric); error function is tangential. NN passed 6,000 training epochs. After training (430 examples) and testing (200 examples), NN determined the error of 0.1066, as shown in Fig. 6

Fig. 6. Error after NN training

But when testing on a control sample, which consisted of 25 examples for each of the five threats, NN determined an error of 0.322. Thus, the NN copes well with Back, Buffer_overflow and Ipsweep attacks, but it does not recognize the Quess_password and Neptune attacks. From the test schedule on the control sample, it can be seen that the first neuron responsible for detecting the Back attack detected four of the five threats (the darker line is an expected solution, and the lighter is the actual one), Fig. 7 (a).

Also, NN recognized all five threats of Buffer_overflow type, fig. 7 (b). The lines on the chart are almost the same, but also one of the threats of Back type is incorrectly assigned by NN to the Buffer_overflow class. The obtained results of the experimental study are presented in Table 1.

Study of network training time versus the number of hidden neurons. The study was carried out on NN with different number of neurons in a hidden layer: from 10 to 55. Experiments were carried out on the following models: Model No. 1 (Initialize Resilent Sigmoid Stepwise Algorithm), Model No. 2 (Randomize Batch Sigmoid Symmetric Algorithm). The results of studies are presented in Table 2.

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Fig. 7. Graph of the resulting neuron of the network:
a – the first one; *b* – the second one

Table 1

Results of NN operation on a control sample

Attack	Number of attacks	Number of detected attacks	Number of recognition errors
Back	5	4	1
Buffer_overflow	5	5	1
Quess_password	5	2	5
Ipsweep	5	4	1
Neptune	5	1	5

Table 2

Dependence of NN training time on the number of hidden neurons

Number of neurons in the hidden layer	Model No. 1		Model No. 2	
	Error	Number of training epochs	Error	Number of training epochs
10	0.1982	20 039	0.1996	6 387
15	0.1994	253	0.2021	2 000
25	0.197	214	0.1993	33
35	0.196	170	0.1977	22
45	0.1964	116	0.1960	18
55	0.199	249	0.193	35

When increasing the number of neurons in the hidden layer, the NN is trained faster, but in some cases, when the optimal amount starts to exceed (> 45), the training rate falls. In addition, model No. 2 is trained much faster than model No. 1. The con-

structed graphs of dependence of the number of epochs on the number of neurons in the hidden layer under different training algorithms are presented in Fig. 8.

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Fig. 8. Dependence of the number of epochs on the number of hidden neurons

Study of training time versus the number of hidden layers. The study was carried out on NN with a different number of hidden layers: from 1 to 4; 15 formal neurons in each. Experiments were carried out on the following models: Model No. 3

(Incremental Training rate 0.4), Model No. 4 (Resilient Training rate 0.8). The initialization algorithm was Randomize, activation function – sigmoid (symmetric). The results of experimental studies are listed in Table 3.

Table 3

Dependence of NN training time on the number of hidden layers

Number of hidden layer	Model No. 3		Model No. 4	
	Error	Number of training epochs	Error	Number of training epochs
1	0.1495	93 775	0.1694	164
2	0.1994	551	0.01394	178
3	0.1279	484	0.1413	224
4	0.1435	2272	0.1478	547

The graphs of the dependence of the number of training epochs on the number of hidden layers based on different training algorithms are plotted and shown in Fig. 9.

From the figure it can be seen that when increasing the number of hidden layers (> 3) in NN, training accelerates only to a certain point, until the layers become too many, then the network begins to slow down. In addition, the model No. 4 is trained almost twice as fast as the model No. 3, but has a bigger error, which results from an increased training rate.

Originality and practical value

The originality lies in the fact that there are found dependencies of the training time (number of epochs) of the multilayer neural network on the number of hidden layers and hidden neurons according to different training algorithms. The practical value is that the network traffic parameters, using the 19-1-25-5 configuration neural network, will allow in real-time to detect the threats of Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune on the computer network and carry out appropriate control.

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Fig. 9. Dependence of the number of training epochs on the number of hidden layers

Conclusions

1. At the preparatory stage, based on the data of the KDDCUP-99 database, the following samples were generated: training (430 examples), test (200 examples), control (25 examples).

2. To determine the attacks (Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune) in the computer network, the Fann Explorer program created NN of 19-1-25-5 configuration, with 19 network traffic parameters inputted; training, testing (error 0.1) and evaluation of the received results (error 0.3) on the corresponding samples were conducted. In particular, the first neuron re-

sponsible for recognizing the Back attack detected four of the five threats.

3. Experimental studies of the dependence of the training time (number of epochs) on the number of hidden neurons (from 10 to 55) on NN were conducted: Model No. 1 (Resilient algorithm), Model No. 2 (Batch algorithm); the Batch algorithm NM is trained three times faster than the NN based on the Resilient algorithm. The experimental studies of the dependence of the training time on the number of hidden layers (from 1 to 4) on the NN were conducted: Model No. 3 (Incremental algorithm), Model No. 4 (Resilient algorithm); the Resilient algorithm NM is trained almost twice as fast as NN by the Incremental algorithm.

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ВИЯВЛЕННЯ ЗАГРОЗ У КОМП'ЮТЕРНІЙ МЕРЕЖІ НА ОСНОВІ БАГАТОШАРОВОЇ НЕЙРОННОЇ МЕРЕЖІ

Мета. Останнім часом все частіше з'являються повідомлення про проникнення в комп'ютерні мережі та атаки на Web-сервери. Атаки поділяють на наступні категорії: DoS, U2R, R2L, Probe. Метою статті є виявлення загроз у комп'ютерній мережі на основі параметрів мережного трафіка з використанням нейромережної технології, що дозволить захистити сервер. **Методика.** Виявлення в комп'ютерній мережі таких загроз, як Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune здійснено на основі аналізу та обробки даних про параметри мережних з'єднань, що використовують стек протоколів TCP/IP, із застосуванням нейронної мережі конфігурації 19-1-25-5 у програмі Fann Explorer. Під час моделювання роботи нейронної мережі використані навчальна (430 прикладів), тестова (200 прикладів) та контрольна (25 прикладів) вибірки, що складені на основі відкритої бази даних KDDCUP-99 із 5 000 000 записів про з'єднання. **Результати.** Створена нейронна мережа на контрольній вибірці визначила похибку в 0,322. Визначено, що мережа конфігурації 19-1-25-5 добре справляється з такими атаками, як Back, Buffer_overflow та Ipsweep. Для розпізнання атак Quess_password і Neptune недостатньо завдання 19 параметрів мережного трафіку. **Наукова новизна.** Отримані залежності часу навчання (кількості епох) нейронної мережі від кількості нейронів у прихованому шарі (від 10 до 55) та кількості прихованих шарів (від 1 до 4). За умови збільшення

кількості нейронів у прихованому шарі нейронна мережа за алгоритмом Batch навчається швидше майже в три рази, ніж нейронна мережа за алгоритмом Resilient. Якщо збільшити кількість прихованих шарів, нейронна мережа за алгоритмом Resilient навчається майже в два рази швидше, ніж за алгоритмом Incremental. **Практична значимість.** На основі параметрів мережного трафіка використання нейронної мережі конфігурації 19-1-25-5 дозволить у реальному часі виявити загрози Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune на комп'ютерну мережу та здійснити відповідний контроль.

Ключові слова: мережний трафік; загроза; нейронна мережа; вибірка; прихований шар; приховані нейрони; алгоритм навчання; кількість епох; похибка

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ВЫЯВЛЕНИЕ УГРОЗ В КОМПЬЮТЕРНОЙ СЕТИ НА ОСНОВЕ МНОГОСЛОЙНОЙ НЕЙРОННОЙ СЕТИ

Цель. В последнее время все чаще появляются сообщения о проникновении в компьютерные сети и атаки на Web-серверы. Атаки подразделяют на следующие категории: DoS, U2R, R2L, Probe. Целью статьи является выявление угроз в компьютерной сети на основе параметров сетевого трафика с использованием нейросетевой технологии, что позволит защитить сервер. **Методика.** Обнаружение в компьютерной сети таких угроз как Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune осуществлено на основе анализа и обработки данных о параметрах сетевых соединений, что используют стек протоколов TCP/IP, с применением нейронной сети конфигурации 19-1-25-5 в программе Fann Explorer. При моделировании работы нейронной сети использованы учебная (430 примеров), тестовая (200 примеров) и контрольная (25 примеров) выборки, составленные на основе открытой базы данных KDDCUP-99 с 5 000 000 записей о соединении. **Результаты.** Созданная нейронная сеть на контрольной выборке определила погрешность в 0,322. Определено, что сеть конфигурации 19-1-25-5 хорошо справляется с такими атаками как Back, Buffer_overflow и Ipsweep. Для распознавания атак Quess_password и Neptune недостаточно задания 19 параметров сетевого трафика. **Научная новизна.** Получены зависимости времени обучения (количества эпох) нейронной сети от количества нейронов в скрытом слое (от 10 до 55) и количества скрытых слоев (от 1 до 4). При условии увеличения количества нейронов в скрытом слое нейронная сеть по алгоритму Batch учится быстрее почти в три раза, чем нейронная сеть по алгоритму Resilient. Если увеличить количество скрытых слоев, нейронная сеть по алгоритму Resilient учится почти в два раза быстрее, чем по алгоритму Incremental. **Практическая значимость.** На основе параметров сетевого трафика использование нейронной сети конфигурации 19-1-25-5 позволит в реальном времени обнаружить угрозы Back, Buffer_overflow, Quess_password, Ipsweep, Neptune на компьютерную сеть и осуществить соответствующий контроль.

Ключевые слова: сетевой трафик; угроза; нейронная сеть; выборка; скрытый слой; скрытые нейроны; алгоритм обучения; количество эпох; погрешность

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